

Stitch Parameter Effects on Interlaminar Fracture Toughness of CFRP Laminates

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ABSTRACT

The double cantilever beam (DCB) tests were executed for stitched CFRP laminates to evaluate the interlaminar fracture toughness (GIC). The stitching parameters (stitch line spacing and pitch) were changed and their effects on interlaminar fracture toughness were examined. (Fig.1) illustrates the size of DCB test specimen.

The DCB tests result are as follows:

1) At one level of equivalent stitch density for several specimens, different types of shape in Load-COD (Crack Opening Displacement) curves were found. It can be concluded that the difference in shape was affected by stitch pitch condition of each stitch lines. On the other hand, their GIC's were not so seriously affected by shape of Load-COD curve.

2) Interlaminar fracture toughness was mainly governed by stitch density. It was confirmed that increase in stitch density in laminates leads to the improvement in GIC

